

Optimization of productivity of three soybean varieties through fertilization in dry land acid soils in South Lampung

Endriani^{1*}, Danarsi Diptaningsari¹, Dian Meithasari¹, Arivin Rivaie¹

¹Lampung Assessment Institute for Agricultural Technology
Jalan Z.A. Pagar Alam No.1a, Rajabasa, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia
Telp. (0721) 701328, Fax: (0721) 705273

*Corresponding author : endriani75@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The large area of dry land acid soils in Lampung area are potentially developed to increase soybean production through phosphate fertilization. The objective was to determine optimal dosage of P fertilizers for growth and yield of soybeans in dry land acid soils. The experiment was conducted in October-December 2016 in Natar Experimental Station, South Lampung District, using factorial randomized block design and replicated 3 times. The treatments consisted of three soybean varieties: soybean varieties (V1 = Grobogan, V2 = Anjasmoro, V3 = Gepak Kuning), and P fertilization (P0 = no fertilizer P, P1 = 50 kg SP36/ha, P2 = 111 kg SP-36/ha, P3 = 222 kg SP-36/ha, P4 = 333 kg SP-36/ha, P5 = 132 kg Rock Phosphate/ha, P6 = 264 kg Rock Phosphate/ha, and P7 = 396 kg Rock Phosphate/ha). Agronomic variables observed were plant growth, plant height, number of leaves, number of root nodules per plant, root length, and yield of dry seeds per hectare. The result showed that interaction of varieties and dosage of P fertilizer affected significantly plant growth. The significant differences between varieties on number of leaves, number of root nodules, root length and yield of dry seeds, but no significantly different for plant growth. Yield of dried seed of varieties of Grobogan, Anjasmoro, Gepak Kuning reached 2.5; 1.4; and 2.0 t/ha, respectively.

Keywords : Acid soils, productivity, rock phosphate, soybean

INTRODUCTION

Soybean production Lampung Province in 2015 was 15.88 thousand tons of dry beans which increased 2.11 thousand tons (15.29%) compared to 2014. Increase of soybean production is due to an increase of harvested areas of 1.58 thousand hectares (13.94%) and an increase in productivity by 0.14 quintal/ha (1.19%) (BPS, 2016). Increase of soybean production does not meet yet the needs of the community. Public consumption reaches 2.5 million tons of dry seeds of soybean, which consists of direct consumption by a population of 2 million tons of soybean dry seeds, animal feed of 3,000 tons of dry seeds of soybean, Seeds of 39,000 tons of dry seeds of soybean, non-food industry of 446,000 tons of grain dried soybeans, and milk of 49,000 tons of dry seeds of soybean (Hasdi, 2015).

The dry land acid soils in Lampung cover areas of 2,650,413 million ha that 912,609 ha are suitable for crops or food area, which can be potentially utilized to increase soybean production. There are several problems in managing soybean cultivation in acid soils, namely high soil acidity, low soil fertility levels, and limited water availability. Optimization of acid soils for better plant growth require the balance of technological innovation and its dissemination (Hidayat et al., 2002; Koesrini et al., 2004). The success of dry land acid soils for food crops cultivation is driven by many factors, such as level of environmental and suitability, attitudes and perceptions of farmers, crafts and tenacity, cultivation technology is good and right, including land preparation. One type of acid soils are quite wide-spread and potential for development of soybean is Ultisols.

The Ultisols in Indonesia around 45.794 million ha or 25% of the total land area of Indonesia that distributed in Borneo, Sumatra, Sulawesi, Java, Maluku, Papua and Nusa Tenggara (Prasetyo and Suriadikarta, 2006). Soybean cultivation in Ultisols often fail if the provision of inorganic fertilizers do not match with organic fertilizers. This is because Ultisols generally have low fertility which is characterized by acidic soil pH, low fertility, low content of Ca, Mg, K, P and Mo, low organic material in soil, and high content of Al, Mn and Fe that are toxic to plants (Soepardi, 1983; Bessho and Bell, 1992).

In acidic soils, phosphate will be compounded in the form of Al-P, Fe-P, while in alkaline soils will be precipitated as calcium phosphate (Ca-P) partially which is poorly soluble. The presence of the phosphate-binding fertilizer is inefficient, so it needs to be given to the plant in large numbers. Application of phosphate into the soil is only absorbed by plants as much as 15-20%. While a large part of P will be entrapped by soil colloids and accumulated in the soil (Drouillon and Merckx, 2003). This will lead to phosphate deficiency for plant growth. One alternative to improve phosphate fertilizer efficiency in soil is to utilize phosphate solvent microorganism group. The microorganisms can dissolve form of unavailable phosphate become available form which can be absorbed by plants.

P nutrient plays a very important role and vital for plant growth in agricultural production systems and food security world (Vance et al., 2003; Radersma and Grierson, 2004; Ulrich et al., 2009). Their functions can not be replaced by other elements in the process of physiology and biochemistry (Syers et al., 2008). All plants need sufficient P during plant growth period (Grant et al., 2001). For legume such as soybeans, P role important role in determining the level of crop production (Norrish and Rosser, 1983; Mosali et al., 2006; Owolade et al., 2006; Peltonen-Sainio et al., 2006; Zeidan, 2007), so that fertilization P is a key component in maximizing crop production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted in October - December 2016 at Natar Experimental Station, Negararatu village, Natar District, South Lampung regency. The materials used were soybean seeds of Grobogan, Anjasmoro and Gepak Kuning varieties derived from Balitkabi Malang; insecticide Marshal 25 ST, manure, dolomite, SP-36 fertilizer, Urea, KCl and Rock Phosphate from Marocco (ingredient of 30.28% P₂O₅). The research used a factorial randomized block design (RAK) and replicated 3 times. The treatment consisted of two factors, first factor was soybean varieties (V1 = Grobogan, V2 = Anjasmoro, V3 = Gepak Kuning), and second factor was P fertilization (P0 = without P fertilizer, P1 = 18 kg P₂O₅/ha equivalent to 50 kg SP-36/ha, P2 = 40 kg P₂O₅/ha equivalent of 111 kg SP-36/ha, P3 = 80 kg P₂O₅/ha equivalent of 222 kg of SP-36/ha, P4 = 120 kg P₂O₅ equivalent of 333 kg of SP-36/ha, P5 = 40 kg P₂O₅/ha equivalent of 132 kg Rock Phosphate/ha, P6 = 80 kg P₂O₅/ha equivalent of 264 kg Rock Phosphate/ha, and P7 = 120 kg P₂O₅/ha equivalent of 396 kg Rock Phosphate/ha).

The tillage was done twice, then a drainage channel was made in each plot (4 x 20 meters). The experimental plots were made with a size of 3 x 5 meters totaling 63 plots. The organic fertilizer (2 t/ha) and KCl fertilizer (100 kg/ha) were applied after the tillage. Direct seed planting was done with a spacing of 40 x 15 cm, filled with 2 seeds per planting hole. The seed treatment was carried out by mixing the seeds with Rhizoplus (5 g/kg of seed) and carbosulfan insecticides (10-15 g/kg of seed). The weed control was managed manually and mechanically. The observations were carried out every two week during growth to harvest, by observing the components of growth and production. The agronomic variables were observed as follow: % of plant growth, plant height, number of leaves, number of nodules per plant, root length and yield per hectare. The data were analyzed with ANOVA F-test, and further test with DMRT (Duncan Multiple Range Test) at the 5% significance level if there is significant difference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of plant growth

The observation of plant growth of three soybean varieties with applying P fertilizers is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of interaction between varieties and P fertilizers on plant growth of three soybean varieties in acid soils, South Lampung

Varieties	Without P fertilizer	50 kg SP-36/ha	111 kg SP-36/ha	222 kg SP-36/ha	132 kg Rock Phosphate /ha	264 kg Rock Phosphate /ha	396 kg Rock Phosphate /ha
	(%)						
Grobogan	93.33 a A	98.29 a A	95.81 a A	96.00 a A	93.52 a A	99.44 a A	97.03 a A
Anjasmoro	99.83a A	92.12a A	92.12 a A	99.28a A	97.78a A	95.96 a B	94.29a A
Gepak Kuning	99.23 a A	97.41 a A	91.81 a A	96.19 a A	95.74 a A	94.71 a A	97.03 a A

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

Three varieties have the plant growth above 90% and there was no significant difference between the varieties. Level of P fertilizer does not show significant differences for the variable of germination of Grobogan variety. There is a treatment effect of P fertilizer for the germination of Anjasmoro, the highest germination is a dose of fertilizer P of 80 kg P_2O_5 /ha well in both of P sources, and significantly different among P fertilizer doses. Level P dosages are no significant differences for Gepak Kuning growth.

The interaction effect of varieties and fertilizers phosphorus on the plant growth occurs in Anjasmoro variety, but not on Grobogan and Gepak Kuning varieties. Environmental factors affect the growth and production of plants, but it is also by genetic factors and the interaction of two factors (Chozin, 2006). Component technology to increase yield of soybean crops in dry land acid soils can be done with using tolerant and high yielding varieties and necessary modified environment. Sudaryanto and Swastika (2007) said that contribution of improved varieties to increase productivity should be easily seen and understood by farmers. Therefore, the assembly of new varieties that have the character of high productivity and tolerance to environmental stress are indispensable in order to increase soybean production. High performance of the plant can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of varieties and P fertilizers on plant height of three soybean varieties in dry land acid soils, South Lampung

Varieties	Without P Fertilizer	50 kg SP-36/ha	111 kg SP-36/ha	222 kg SP-36/ha	132 kg Rock Phosphate/ha	264 kg Rock Phosphate/ha	396 kg Rock Phosphate/ha
(cm)							
Grobogan	22.90 b A	18.10 b C	21.26 b A	21.66 b A	19.86 b B	19.06 c B	19.86 b B
Anjasmoro	36.80 a A	34.66 a A	33.80 a A	36.86 a A	34.40 a A	37.53 a A	31.00 a A
Gepak Kuning	24.42 b A	28.04 c B	26.12 ab AB	26.40 b A	30.03 a C	28.72 b B	29.53 a C

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

The Gepak Kuning variety showed significant differences to the treatment dose of P fertilizer. The Anjasmoro variety at all dose levels of P fertilizer showed no significant differences for plant height variable and Anjasmoro showed highest plants compared with Grobogan and Gepak Kuning varieties. The dose of P fertilizer did not significantly affect the plant height of Anjasmoro variety, but it affected Grobogan and Gepak Kuning varieties. Rock phosphate is effective as well as chemical P fertilizers such as TSP and SP-36, and has a better residual effect, cheaper prices, saving labor for administration at a time in large numbers and are not necessarily given every growing season (Kisitu, 1991; Idris, 1995; Akinton et al., 2003).

Table 3. Effect of varieties and P fertilizers on the number of leaves of three soybean varieties in dryland acid soils, South Lampung

Varieties	Without P fertilizer	50 kg SP-36/ha	111 kg SP-36/ha	222 kg SP-36/ha	132 kg Rock Phosphate/ha	264 kg Rock Phosphate/ha	396 kg Rock Phosphate/ha
(number of leaves/plant)							
Grobogan	22.66 a A	25.11 a A	23.51 a A	23.46 a A	24.13 a A	24.44 a A	23.08 a A
Anjasmoro	24.26 b A	26.13 b A	27.60 b A	26.33 b A	24.93 a A	28.73 b A	27.53 b A
Gepak Kuning	30.33 c A	33.60 c A	28.87 c A	29.00 c A	33.33 b A	31.27 c A	27.47 b A

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

Application of P fertilizer did not differentsignificantly on number of leaves. The leaves are the important tissues that photosynthesis process occurs. Characters morphophysiological crops such as leaf thickness and rate of growth of the plants, the plants allegedly character affect the level of productivity and

rate of photosynthesis. Sufficient supply of nutrients that help the process of photosynthesis in plants producing organic compounds to be converted in the form of ATP during respiration, then the ATP is used to help grow crops.

Table 4. Effect of varieties and P fertilizers on the number of root nodules of three soybean varieties in dryland acid soils, South Lampung

Varieties	Without P fertilizer	50 kg SP-36/ha	111 kg SP-36/ha	222 kg SP-36/ha	132 kg Rock Phosphate /ha	264 kg Rock Phosphate /ha	396 kg Rock Phosphate /ha
	number of root nodules/plant						
Grobogan	25.00 b A	26.33 b A	27.33 b A	26.00 a A	13.00 a A	19.33 a A	23.33 a A
Anjasmoro	15.33 a A	21.33 a A	21.67 a A	26.33 a A	24.93 b A	28.73 b A	27.53 b A
Gepak Kuning	30.33 c A	33.60 c A	28.87 c A	29.00 b A	33.33 c A	31.27 c A	27.47 b A

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at P<0.05 by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

The Gepak kuning variety tend to have a number of nodules higher than two other varieties. Factors genotype did not significantly affect the number of root nodules. Environmental factors, such as rainfall during the growing period of the establishment of the number of root nodules. Environmental conditions of moist soil around the roots to support the proliferation of bacteria to infect the emergence of root nodules. Number three varieties of root nodules quite a lot. For variable root length measured at maximum vegetative phase (7 weeks after planting) can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Effect of varieties and P fertilizers on root length of three soybean varieties of in the dry land acid soils, South Lampung

Varieties	Without P fertilizer	50 kg SP-36/ha	111 kg SP-36/ha	222 kg SP-36/ha	132 kg Rock Phosphate/ha	264 kg Rock Phosphate /ha	396 kg Rock Phosphate /ha
	(cm)						
Grobogan	19.00a A	20.83 a A	16.16 a A	16.43ab A	22.16 a A	20.83 a A	17.00 ab A
Anjasmoro	17.70 ab A	18.60 a A	15.50 b A	17.76 a A	14.33 b A	15.00 b A	19.66 a A
Gepak Kuning	17.33 b A	14.33 ab A	15.43 bc A	16.23 ab A	12.90 b A	16.83 b A	15.83 c A

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at P<0.05 by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

The Grobogan variety has long roots longer than Anjasmoro and Gepak Kuning. Soybean root length associated with the environment grows, among other rooting area water availability, soil nutrient levels. Plants with ability to absorb Ca (Calcium) in large quantities can improve the process of dissolving phosphate. Plants that have a high density of roots that can absorb P well, so that the equilibrium in the soil will be maintained and dissolving P becomes high (Wijanarko, 2015). P element absorbed by the crops from fertilizer during morning and evening when the humidity rises, while at noon fertilizer with a high concentration tends to be hypertonic because the water evaporates, so the fertilizer can not be absorbed up by plants.

Performance of plant production

The yield among three varieties was not significantly different. Grobogan variety including soybean with large seed size, with weight of 100 grains of 18 g gives the highest tile dried seed production, followed by Gepak Kuning. Gepak Kuning has soybean with small seed size with weight of 100 grains 8.3 g, while Anjasmoro has soybean with big seed size with weight of 100 grains 16 g. Statistically these three varieties showed no significant difference in yield for the production of dry weight seeds. The result of production conversion per hectare is obtained by average production of dried seed varieties of Grobogan 2.5 tons per hectare. Anjasmoro varieties produce dry seed production per hectare of 1.4 tons per hectare and Gepak Kuning produce 2.0 tons per hectare (Table 6). The seeds are formed in pods along with it continues ripening (Sumarno and Mansuri, 2007).

Table 6. Effect of varieties and P fertilizers on dried seed production of three soybean varieties of in the dry land acid soils, South Lampung

Varieties	Without P Fertilizer	50 kg SP-36/ha	111 kg SP-36/ha	222 kg SP-36/ha	132 kg Rock Phosphate/ha	264 kg Rock Phosphate/ha	396 kg Rock Phosphate/ha
(kg/ha)							
Grobogan	2,236a A	2,652 a A	2,773 a A	3,185 a A	2,210 a A	1,989a A	2,470 a A
Average	2,502						
Anjasmoro	621 c A	977b A	2,379 ab A	2,584 a A	1,187b A	781b A	1,315b A
Average	1,406						
Gepak Kuning	3,060 ab A	1,807 b A	1,240 c A	3,693 a A	847 c A	740 c A	2,700 ab A
Average	2,012						

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at P<0.05 by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

The effectiveness of natural phosphates can be assessed by calculating Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (RAE), by comparing the effect of natural phosphate with TSP or SP-36 (Suzette et al., 2006). The P requirement of soybean plant in acid soil varies widely, depending on its availability in the soil. Wijanarko and Taufiq (2008) suggested that the critical limit of soil P for soybean crops in Ultisols based on using Bray I extraction is 5 and 23 ppm P_2O_5 , whereas using Bray II extraction is 11 and 38 ppm P_2O_5 . Based on this critical limit the class P available to grade the availability of low, medium, and high respectively were <5 ppm, 5-23 ppm, and > 23 ppm P_2O_5 with method I and <11, 11 -38 and > 38 ppm P_2O_5 with Bray II method. Provision of organic material in the form of manure or plant waste can increase the solubility of natural phosphate and the availability of P in soil. The results of Wijanarko (2015) showed that mixing of organic material in the form of soy biomass in Bojonegoro with natural phosphate of 105 kg P_2O_5 increased soybean yield on Ultisols Lampung.

The increase of seed weight reached 130% compared with treatment without P fertilizer. The effect of natural phosphate on soybean yield in Bojonegoro was even higher than that of SP-36 and Lamongan natural phosphate. The results of Biswas and Narayanasami (2006) showed that mixing of natural phosphate and compost could increase the P availability in soil with effectiveness of 61.4% higher than that of diamonium phosphate fertilizer, and increase RAE by 173% compared to TSP fertilizer. The results of Wijanarko (2015) showed that mixing of organic material in the form of soy biomass in Bojonegoro natural phosphate with dosage of 105 kg P_2O_5 increased soybean yield on Ultisols Lampung. The increase of seed weight reached 130% compared with treatment without P fertilizer. The effect of Bojonegoro natural phosphate on soybean yield was even higher than that of SP-36 and Lamongan natural phosphate.

CONCLUSIONS

Significant effect on interaction between varieties and P fertilizer occurred on plant growth percentage, plant height, root length, and dry seed production per plot. The soybean yield of Grobogan, Anjasmoro and Gepak Kuning varieties reached 2.5, 1.4 and 2.0 t/ha, respectively. The advantages of rock phosphate include are the price of each kg of P_2O_5 cheaper, can be used directly, its effectiveness is almost the same as SP-36, it saves the use of labor because it is applied in large quantities and should not be given every season, and has residual effect. The disadvantage is having a low solubility rate.

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